

External Reserves and Trade Dynamics: Pathways to Sustainable Growth in Nigeria

Karimo Perry Erepano(ACA)
ereskarimo@yahoo.com

Chukwu Vera Amuche (ACA)
amuchev.chukwu@gmail.com

Williams Nachor Handel
handlel.williams@iaue.edu.ng

Emubosa John Ogheneovo
Emubosaogheneovo100@gmail.com

Abstract

This study investigates the relationship external reserves, trade dynamics and sustainable growth in Nigeria between from 2000 to 2022. Utilizing Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test for stationarity, vector auto regression (VAR) model and pairwise Granger causality tests, the research reveals a significant unidirectional causal relationship between HDI and EXR, indicating that human development improves external reserves. Nevertheless, fluctuations in external reserves and oil import trade have a negative impact on HDI, whereas non-oil export trade has a positive influence on human development. The model's explanatory Rsquared of 86% confirms the relevance of these variables in understanding economic dynamics. The study recommends prioritising human development initiatives, diversifying the economy, strengthening external reserve management, encouraging trade liberalisation, and continuously monitoring economic policies to foster sustainable growth in Nigeria. The research offers valuable policy implications for enhancing economic resilience and improving the quality of life for citizens. The study also highlights the need for effective management of foreign reserves and diversification of trade activities to promote sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

Keywords: Human Development (HDI), External Reserve(EXR), Trade Dynamics ,Sustainable Economic Growth.

Introduction

Foreign reserves and trade dynamics are becoming increasingly important as Nigeria navigates its economic terrain. External reserves are financial assets that a government possesses in foreign currencies. These reserves are crucial for sustaining currency stability, limiting inflation rates, and facilitating commerce. Effective management of these reserves can lead to huge economic advantages. Nigeria's external reserves rebounded from the COVID-19 pandemic collapse in 2021, reaching roughly \$40 billion. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has recently emphasised raising reserves using multiple policy measures, including intervention in the FX market. The movement of commodities and services between Nigeria and the rest of the world is governed by trade dynamics.

The management of external reserves is vital to Nigeria's economy, acting as a safety net against financial disturbances and promoting sustainable development. These reserves, largely generated from crude oil exports, have historically been crucial in stabilising the Nigerian economy, especially amidst the erratic global oil prices. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) found that foreign reserves are important for covering balance of payments deficits and supporting a competitive exchange rate, which is essential for meeting macroeconomic goals (IMF, 2012). Numerous studies have shown that external reserves play a significant role in Nigeria's ongoing economic development.

Research demonstrates a positive correlation between external reserves and economic growth in both the short and long run (Akinboyo et al., 2016). Specifically, a 1% rise in external reserves results in a 0.15% boost in economic growth (Akinboyo et al., 2016).

Furthermore, over the long term, external reserves are identified as a critical factor affecting Nigeria's economic growth, responding positively with a 0.22% increase to modifications in external reserves.

Interestingly, while external reserves have a positive impact on economic growth, the effects of external debt are less obvious. Some research indicates that external debt can hinder economic growth (Ndubuaku et al., 2021; Osadume & Ovuokeroye, 2021), whereas other studies suggest a positive influence (Denis et al., 2017). This disparity highlights the complex characteristics of Nigeria's economy and the need for diligent management of both reserves and debt.

Nigeria's dependence on oil exports, along with the interactions between oil and non-oil import and export activities, significantly affects its trade landscape. Maintaining sufficient external reserves is essential for the country's sustainable economic development. Effective governance, sound economic practices, and robust anti-corruption measures are necessary for successful management of these reserves.

Furthermore, minimising local borrowing, makes judicious use of borrowed resources, and improving debt management strategies can all help to foster long-term economic growth (Denis et al., 2017). Moreover, Nwosa (2017) notes that sufficient external reserves can give the government the financial flexibility needed to invest in infrastructure, healthcare, and education, which are essential for long-term economic growth and development.

High levels of external reserves enable countries to engage in international trade more effectively, as they can meet foreign currency obligations (Abdullateef & Waheed, 2010).

Despite the positive correlation between external reserves and economic growth, the management of these reserves is fraught with challenges. The costs associated with maintaining high levels of reserves can be substantial, as the returns on foreign exchange reserves are typically lower than those on domestic investments (Nwamuo, 2023). Furthermore, the volatility of oil prices and the global economic landscape have made it increasingly difficult for Nigeria to maintain stable reserves, thus complicating the path toward sustainable development.

Statement of Problem

For the past twenty years, changes in trade dynamics and foreign reserve levels have had a considerable influence on Nigeria's economic climate. Nigeria's foreign reserves have changed dramatically between 2000 and 2022. They were around \$9.39 billion in 2000, to a high of \$53.00 billion in 2008, decreased to \$26.99 billion in 2016, climbed to \$42.59 billion in 2021, and then declined once more to \$36.61 billion in 2022 (Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin). The subject of how external reserves assist long-term economic development is strongly put into doubt by this instability. Although the value of foreign reserves is accepted, the scientific community cannot agree on how exactly they effect economic progress. According to some scholars, having sufficient foreign reserves will enhance investor confidence and stimulate investment, which will support economic growth (Elhiraika & Ndikumana, 2007). On the other hand, others believe that retaining huge reserves would divert cash away from important domestic needs like healthcare and education, which could limit economic progress (Osabuohien & Egwakhe, 2008). This mismatch demonstrates the complexity of Nigeria's economic condition and underlines the requirement for efficient management of both reserves and trade dynamics.

The links between the import and export of oil, non-oil imports, and external reserves have also not been properly investigated. Nigeria is heavily reliant on oil exports, so it is critical to understand how these trade dynamics mix with foreign reserves to affect the country's overall economic performance in order to design successful policy measures. This research attempts to examine the influence of Nigeria's external reserves on its economic performance from 2000 to 2022. In order to generate insights that will impact policy decisions aimed at optimising reserve management for sustainable development, this research looks at how changes in external reserves affect economic stability and growth while taking trade dynamics into consideration.

enough foreign reserves will enhance investor confidence and stimulate investment, hence fostering economic growth (Elhiraika & Ndikumana, 2007). Conversely, some contend that maintaining substantial reserves may divert resources from urgent domestic concerns such as healthcare and education, thereby hindering economic progress (Osabuohien & Egwakhe, 2008). This mismatch highlights the intricacy of Nigeria's economic condition and underscores the necessity for effective management of both reserves and trade dynamics.

The interconnections among oil imports and exports, non-oil imports, and foreign reserves remain inadequately analysed. Nigeria's economy is significantly reliant on oil exports; therefore, it is crucial to understand how these trade dynamics interact with foreign reserves to influence the nation's overall economic performance for the formulation of effective policy measures.

This research attempts to examine the influence of Nigeria's external reserves on its economic performance from 2000 to 2022. In order to generate insights that will impact policy decisions aimed at optimising reserve management for sustainable development, this research looks at how changes in external reserves affect economic stability and growth while taking trade dynamics into consideration.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

This study aims to explore how external reserves influence sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

The specific objectives are as follows:

- i. to assess the influence of external reserves on the Human Development Index (HDI) in Nigeria.
- ii. to analyse the effect of oil import trade on economic growth in Nigeria.
- iii. to evaluate the impact of non-oil import trade on economic growth in Nigeria.
- iv. to explore the relationship between oil export trade and economic growth in Nigeria.
- v. to examine the influence of non-oil export trade on economic growth in Nigeria.

1.3 Hypotheses of the Study

H0: There is no significant relationship between external reserves or the explanatory variables (oil import trade, non-oil import trade, oil export trade, and non-oil export trade) and Human Development in Nigeria.

2 Conceptual Framework

2.1 External Reserves

Foreign currency reserves, also referred to as external reserves, are the stock of foreign currency assets owned by a country's central bank or monetary authority. External reserves are viewed as national assets and crucial for managing economic stability. They play a crucial role in ensuring economic stability, especially in developing nations like Nigeria, where external shocks can significantly impair performance. They serve various purposes, including buffering against external shocks, facilitating trade, and attracting investment. In Nigeria, the reliance on oil exports has made foreign reserves sensitive to global oil price swings, emphasising the importance of diversifying the economy to lessen exposure to external shocks.

2.1.1 Oil Import Trade

Oil import trade refers to the volume and value of crude oil and petroleum products imported into Nigeria. Despite being one of the largest oil producers in Africa, Nigeria still imports refined petroleum products due to inadequate refining capacity. This reliance on oil imports can create vulnerabilities in the economy, particularly when global oil prices fluctuate. The cost of imports can strain external reserves, affecting the country's balance of payments and overall economic stability. As noted by Abdullateef and Waheed (2010), the dependence on oil imports has implications for Nigeria's trade balance and foreign exchange reserves, highlighting the need for improved domestic refining capabilities to reduce import dependency.

2.1.2 Non-Oil Import Trade

Non-oil import trade encompasses all imports excluding oil, including manufactured goods, agricultural products, and services. This sector is vital for diversifying the economy and reducing reliance on oil. Increased non-oil imports can lead to greater variety and availability of goods, but

they can also put pressure on external reserves if not managed effectively. The Central Bank of Nigeria has emphasised the importance of balancing oil and non-oil imports to maintain economic stability and ensure sustainable growth. As highlighted by the IMF (2003), "a diversified import structure can help mitigate risks associated with external shocks.

2.1.3 Oil Export Trade

Oil export trade is a cornerstone of Nigeria's economy, accounting for a significant portion of government revenue and foreign exchange earnings. The volatility of global oil prices directly impacts Nigeria's external reserves and overall economic health. The reliance on oil exports makes the economy susceptible to price fluctuations, which can lead to instability in external reserves. According to Nwosa (2017), oil exports are critical for Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings, but over-reliance on this sector poses risks for sustainable economic growth.

2.1.4 Non-Oil Export Trade

Non-oil export trade includes all exports excluding oil, such as agricultural products, textiles, and manufactured goods. Promoting non-oil exports is essential for diversifying Nigeria's economy and reducing vulnerability to oil price shocks. The government has implemented various policies to encourage non-oil exports, recognising their potential to enhance foreign exchange earnings and contribute to economic growth. As noted by Musibau (2015), diversifying export products beyond oil is crucial for Nigeria's long-term economic resilience and sustainability.

2.1.5 Sustainable Economic Growth

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 8), which promotes sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all. Sustainable economic growth, as articulated in SDG 8, emphasises the need for inclusive growth that provides opportunities for all segments of society while ensuring environmental sustainability. This involves

not only increasing GDP but also improving living standards, reducing inequality, and ensuring that economic growth does not come at the expense of future generations. Human Development Index (HDI), measuring the overall progress and well-being of a country's inhabitants.

HDI incorporates indicators of health (life expectancy), education (years of schooling), and standard of living (GNI per capita). As such, it reflects the broader impacts of economic growth on human welfare.

2.2 Theoretical framework

2.2.1 Balance of Payments Theory

Balance of Payments theory is crucial for grasping the importance of external reserves in an economy. This theory posits that a country's economic stability is closely linked to its ability to manage its balance of payments, which includes trade balances, capital flows, and reserves (Obstfeld & Rogoff, 1996). In the context of Nigeria, BOP theory explains how external reserves influence economic growth through trade balances. For instance, oil export trade significantly contributes to Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings, impacting the accumulation of external reserves. Conversely, oil and non-oil import trade affect the outflow of foreign currency, which can deplete reserves. Analysing these dynamics helps to understand how effective management of external reserves can stabilise the economy and promote sustainable growth.

2.2.2 Theory of Trade Liberalisation

Trade liberalisation theory claims that reducing trade barriers may improve economic development by boosting efficiency and competitiveness (Krugman & Obstfeld, 2009). This theory underlines the role of exports and imports in driving economic success. The notion of trade liberalisation explains how external reserves, impacted by oil exports, might promote commerce by supplying the required foreign money for purchases. Additionally, studying

the dynamics of non-oil import and export commerce in connection to external reserves helps emphasise the significance of diversifying the economy to ensure sustainable development.

2.3 Empirical Review

Ndubuisi's (2017) paper evaluates the influence of foreign debt on Nigeria's economic development from 1985 to 2015. Data from secondary sources includes gross domestic product, external debt services, external debt stock, external reserve, and exchange rate. The results show that debt service payment has a negative impact on economic growth, but external debt stock has a positive impact. The report advises government strategies to strengthen the business climate, control debt, and substitute external borrowing for human capital development.

Nteegah and Ebimotimi's (2017) investigation into Nigeria's foreign currency reserves and trade from 1980–2015 reveals that international commerce greatly influences the country's reserves. Foreign reserves were driven by oil imports, non-oil imports, oil exports, and currency rates, while oil and non-oil imports significantly damaged them. The study proposes extending Nigeria's export base and reducing frivolous imports as measures to build foreign reserves and explore the effect of external reserves on economic growth.

Akpan (2016) evaluates the influence of various macroeconomic variables, including exchange rate, GDP, inflation rate, total trade, investment, unemployment, and external debt, on Nigeria's external reserves, utilising data from 2004 to 2014. The analysis reveals that gross domestic product and exchange rate have a significant positive influence on the quantity of external reserves in Nigeria. Egbulonu and Akamike (2018) assess the influence of foreign reserve management on economic growth in Nigeria from 1990 to 2015. The research explores the contemporaneous connection between economic growth and three macroeconomic variables: the foreign reserve, inflation, and currency rate, using autoregressive distributed lag. The outcome of the limits test

demonstrates that there is a persistent link between the variables. The study finds that although exchange rates and inflation have a detrimental effect on economic growth, foreign reserves have a favourable, albeit statistically tiny, benefit. The limits test result demonstrates the existence of a long-term link between the variables. The research reveals that foreign reserves favourably impact economic growth, although statistically insignificantly, whereas exchange rates and inflation have a detrimental effect. Osabuohien & Egwakhe (2008) study the foreign reserves-economy link thesis has sparked dispute owing to insufficient theoretical and empirical consensus. This article presents an economic appraisal and empirical insight into the issue in Nigeria. To achieve this, the article relied on secondary data from the CBN statistics bulletin (1994–2005). The outputs provided demonstrated that external reserves surpassing the three-month benchmark equivalent was in excess; its keeping cost was excessive. In addition, the data revealed a dual-fold interpretation of the analyses: 1) The keeping of external reserves does improve exchange rate stability; 2) a positive association exists between external reserves and exports; nevertheless, the relationship was not significant, thereby implying that exports were not encouraged considerably by the nation's foreign reserves. According to the article, domestic production efficiency is critical to improving macroeconomic performance, not external reserve accumulation.

On the other hand, Ojiako (2020) studies the link existing between foreign reserves and economic performance in Nigeria, spanning a data period of 1981–2018. The research uses the boundaries test approach to co-integration via the implementation of the ARDL model. Accordingly, the study suggests that a long-run link exists between economic performance and foreign reserves. Also, the analysis demonstrates that Nigeria's economic performance had a significant and negative reaction to changes in foreign reserves. However, Ibrahim et al. (2022) research examines Nigeria's unconstrained ECM from 1986 to 2020. They employ the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and a descriptive method to seek for patterns. It finds that economic growth rate and foreign

reserves fluctuate, with external reserves being more prominent. In the long run, all explanatory factors are major predictors of economic development in Nigeria. Economic growth is favourably sensitive to changes in foreign reserves, inflation rate, and GDP lag, while adversely reacting to exchange rate changes. According to the research, government assistance is needed to improve productivity and manage inflation.

Research Gap

The research gap in this study is that scholars don't agree on how external reserves affect Nigeria's economic growth, especially when economic conditions change and other trade factors interact with each other. This is because previous studies have mostly looked at single relationships without looking at how external reserves, oil and non-oil trade dynamics, and sustainable economic growth all work together.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The ex-post facto research design was selected and the researchers utilize secondary data. The research employed secondary data for a period of 23 years, from 2000 to 2022. The data were gathered from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, World Bank databases, and relevant government publications. This extended period allows for a thorough investigation of trends and linkages between external reserves, trade dynamics, and human development.

3.2 Model Specification

The model in its econometric linear form can be written

$$HDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1(ER) + \beta_2(OIT) + \beta_3(NOIT) + \beta_4(OET) + \beta_5(NOET) + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$HDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log(ER) + \beta_2 \log(OIT) + \beta_3 \log(NOIT) + \beta_4 \log(OET) + \beta_5 \log(NOET) + \mu \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

HDI = Human Development Index

EXR = logarithm of external reserves

OMT = logarithm of oil import trade

NOMT = logarithm of non-oil import trade

OET = logarithm of oil export trade

NOET = logarithm of non-oil export trade

β_0 = constant/intercept term

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$ = coefficients of the parameter estimates (slope)

μ = error or disturbance term

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

<i>UNIT ROOT TEST RESULTS TABLE (ADF)</i>			
Variables	T-Statistic	Decision	1st Diff
HDI	-4.3437	1(1)	stationary
LEXR	-2.7869	1(1)	stationary
OMT	-4.4174	1(1)	stationary
NOMT	-3.679	1(1)	stationary
OET	-3.1369	1(1)	stationary
NOET	-4.308	1(1)	stationary

The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test was applied to guarantee data stationarity and prevent the issue of spurious regression. The Augmented dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test was utilised to guarantee data stationarity and prevent the issue of spurious regression as the data for the study is time series.

Table 2

Sample: 2000 - 2022

Included observations: 23

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Endogenous variables: HDI EXR OMT NOMT OET NOET

Deterministic assumptions: Case 2: Cointegrating relationship includes a constant

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	Prob.**
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Critical Value
None *	0.987	218.008	103.847	0.000
At most 1 *	0.964	127.280	76.973	0.000
At most 2 *	0.742	57.502	54.079	0.024
At most 3	0.487	29.038	35.193	0.198
At most 4	0.402	15.022	20.262	0.225
At most 5	0.182	4.209	9.165	0.382

Trace test indicates 3 cointegrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

The cointegration analysis shows a significant relationship between variables such as the Human Development Index (HDI), external reserves, oil import and export trade, and non-oil export trade in Nigeria from 2000 to 2022. The Johansen cointegration test results show three cointegrating equations, indicating a long-run equilibrium relationship. The analysis suggests that changes in external reserves and trade activities have a sustained impact on the Human Development Index in Nigeria. The analysis assumes a constant for long-run dynamics.

Fig 1 Normality test

Source: Author's computation using EViews 13

The normal distribution of the residuals is shown by Figure 1 above, where the probability (0.185532) of the Jaque-Bera statistics is more than 5%. This is encouraging because it demonstrates that our OLS estimates are unbiased, t-statistics and confidence intervals are robust, as well as prediction intervals.

Table 3

	HDI	EXR	OMT	NOMT	OET	NOET
HDI(-1)	0.9171 -0.1854 [4.94703]	2.6516 -0.4805 [5.51902]	-0.0155 -0.9220 [-0.01686]	-0.4731 -0.4188 [-1.12954]	1.9619 -0.6349 [3.09037]	-0.0373 -1.0044 [-0.03712]
EXR(-1)	0.0334 -0.0464 [0.71880]	0.7423 -0.1203 [6.16965]	0.3372 -0.2309 [1.46051]	0.3027 -0.1049 [2.88640]	0.2966 -0.1590 [1.86544]	0.5303 -0.2515 [2.10844]
OMT(-1)	0.0520 -0.0698 [0.74557]	0.3742 -0.1808 [2.06958]	0.4089 -0.3470 [1.17838]	-0.0363 -0.1576 [-0.23033]	0.3842 -0.2389 [1.60787]	0.4365 -0.3780 [1.15471]
NOMT(-1)	-0.2014	0.1436	0.5734	0.3520	-0.4180	0.2261

	-0.0766	-0.1985	-0.3809	-0.1730	-0.2623	-0.4149
	[-2.62959]	[0.72328]	[1.50549]	[2.03464]	[-1.59392]	[0.54496]
OET(-1)	-0.2248	-0.6328	-0.2202	-0.0556	-0.2282	-0.3679
	-0.0909	-0.2356	-0.4522	-0.2054	-0.3113	-0.4926
	[-2.47239]	[-2.68585]	[-0.48699]	[-0.27047]	[-0.73311]	[-0.74692]
NOET(-1)	0.1726	-0.1997	-0.0795	0.2893	0.1844	0.3039
	-0.0529	-0.1371	-0.2631	-0.1195	-0.1811	-0.2866
	[3.26372]	[-1.45655]	[-0.30207]	[2.42133]	[1.01790]	[1.06043]
C	3.2330	8.1148	-0.9363	3.2490	12.8027	-2.6984
	-0.9916	-2.5698	-4.9315	-2.2400	-3.3956	-5.3722
	[3.26044]	[3.15782]	[-0.18985]	[1.45044]	[3.77038]	[-0.50230]
R-squared	0.8628	0.9743	0.9220	0.9783	0.9259	0.9456
Adj. R-squared	0.8080	0.9641	0.8908	0.9695	0.8963	0.9239
Sum sq. resid	0.0654	0.4390	1.6167	0.3336	0.7665	1.9186
S.E. equation	0.0660	0.1711	0.3283	0.1491	0.2261	0.3576
F-statistic	15.7272	94.9589	29.5403	112.4399	31.2501	43.4959
Log likelihood	32.7904	11.8408	-2.4993	14.8622	5.7100	-4.3824
Akaike AIC	-2.3446	-0.4401	0.8636	-0.7147	0.1173	1.0348
Schwarz SC	-1.9974	-0.0929	1.2107	-0.3676	0.4644	1.3819
Mean dependent	0.4574	15.5252	14.2515	15.4313	15.9898	13.1362
S.D. dependent	0.1506	0.9027	0.9933	0.8546	0.7020	1.2965
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)			0.0000			
Determinant resid covariance			0.0000			
Log likelihood			86.9855			
Akaike information criterion			-4.0896			
Schwarz criterion			-2.0067			
Number of coefficients			42			

The VAR model's results, with a coefficient of 0.9171 and a t-statistic of 4.94703, imply that the lagged Human Development Index (HDI) significantly positively affects the current HDI. This suggests that improvements in human evolution are likely to continue across time. However, the t-statistics of 0.71880 and 0.74557 for external reserves (EXR) and oil import trade (OMT) show that they have no statistically significant impact on the HDI. On the other hand, oil export trade (OET) has a strong negative effect with a coefficient of -0.2248 and a t-statistic of -2.47239, while non-oil import trade (NOMT) negatively influences HDI with a coefficient of -0.2014 and a t-statistic of -2.62959. On the other hand, with a coefficient of 0.1726 and a t-statistic of 3.26372, non-oil export trade

(NOET) has a positive impact on HDI. Overall, the model's high R-squared values of 86% and excellent explanatory power demonstrate that the variables included adequately explain the fluctuations in the HDI, highlighting the need for policies that regulate the effects of imports on human development and encourage exports of goods other than oil.

Table 4

Null Hypothesis:	F-Statistic	Prob.	Direction
EXR does not Granger Cause HDI	0.0196	0.8902	
HDI does not Granger Cause EXR	16.6213	0.0006	Unidirectional
OMT does not Granger Cause HDI	0.7311	0.4032	
HDI does not Granger Cause OMT	0.4600	0.5058	Non-directional
NOMT does not Granger Cause HDI	0.3960	0.5366	
HDI does not Granger Cause NOMT	0.0000	0.9995	Non-directional
OET does not Granger Cause HDI	0.0044	0.9480	
HDI does not Granger Cause OET	4.2278	0.0538	Unidirectional
NOET does not Granger Cause HDI	2.2430	0.1506	
HDI does not Granger Cause NOET	0.1106	0.7431	Non-directional

The extended Pairwise Granger Causality Tests show a significant unidirectional causal relationship from the Human Development Index (HDI) to external reserves (EXR), indicating that improvements in human development contribute to enhanced external reserves, while fluctuations in external reserves and oil import trade negatively impact HDI, whereas non-oil export trade positively influences human development outcomes in Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

This study examines the relationship between Nigeria's foreign reserves, oil imports, non-oil imports, oil exports, and human development. According to the VAR model, foreign reserves and oil imports have a negative impact on human development, but non-oil export trade benefits the human development index. As evidenced by the fact that growing HDI promotes greater economic stability and foreign reserves, human development has a significant impact on both oil export commerce and external reserves. The findings show a strong unidirectional causal relationship between Human Development and external reserves, as well as a significant impact of external reserves on the HDI. This illustrates that advances in human development have a favourable impact on the establishment of foreign reserves, which strengthens economic stability. The findings align with Osabuohien and Egwakhe's (2008) research, demonstrating that excessive dependence on foreign reserves can syphon funds away from essential local expenditures in healthcare and education. On the other side, non-oil export commerce has a beneficial influence on human development outcomes, but changes in oil import trade and external reserves have a negative impact. To reduce Nigeria's vulnerability to oil price shocks, the research suggests diversifying Nigeria's economic base and expanding non-oil exports. Policymakers should prioritise human development projects, responsibly manage foreign reserves, and apply approaches that promote a varied trading environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations can be made to enhance sustainable economic growth in Nigeria:

1. Policymakers should prioritize investments in education, healthcare, and social services to enhance the Human Development Index, leading to economic stability, foreign reserves, and sustainable growth.
2. Diversify its economy by promoting non-oil exports and developing sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, and services to reduce dependency on oil revenues and mitigate price fluctuations.
3. The government should enhance external reserves management to maintain economic stability, stabilize the currency, and build resilience against external shocks through prudent fiscal and monetary policies.
4. Nigeria should promote trade liberalization by reducing trade barriers and promoting free trade agreements, thereby enhancing trade dynamics, attracting foreign investment, and stimulating economic growth.
5. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of economic policies are crucial for assessing their effectiveness in promoting human development and economic stability, ensuring alignment with sustainable development goals.

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Appendix						
	<i>HDI</i>	<i>EXR</i>	<i>OMT</i>	<i>NOMT</i>	<i>OET</i>	<i>NOET</i>
1	0	13.6011	12.30509	13.54659	14.4683	10.11952
2	0	13.83182	12.37627	13.9298	14.42525	10.24027
3	0	13.63787	12.7986	13.95613	14.31595	11.45881
4	0.449	13.65455	12.89652	14.33509	14.91182	11.45928
5	0.461	14.58251	12.67017	14.32769	15.31725	11.63788
6	0.468	15.13268	13.58899	14.51044	15.7813	11.57078
7	0.475	15.50843	13.47398	14.69008	15.78835	11.80257
8	0.479	15.63358	13.55184	14.96092	15.90867	12.20236
9	0.482	15.62732	14.08975	15.18228	16.10418	13.17279
10	0.486	15.63122	13.882	15.21366	15.90805	13.12409
11	0.488	15.38267	14.3792	15.58324	16.24036	13.47436
12	0.494	15.4109	14.92855	15.78842	16.47739	13.72505
13	0.499	15.73209	14.93532	15.61063	16.47297	13.68692
14	0.504	15.69721	14.70315	15.66848	16.46394	13.93788
15	0.513	15.57699	14.61084	15.84134	16.301	13.76953
16	0.52	15.54339	14.36087	15.96594	15.91775	13.40102
17	0.526	15.90703	14.68446	15.67905	15.91706	13.39513
18	0.528	16.46644	14.77695	15.82563	16.37376	13.88774
19	0.53	16.54559	15.1201	15.99976	16.66517	14.16994
20	0.532	16.43388	15.07816	16.59757	16.63112	14.98088
21	0.539	16.4446	14.81504	16.69483	16.21868	14.25727
22	0.542	16.61855	15.70985	16.53496	16.63315	14.71844
23	0.548	16.55481	16.10261	16.59299	17.00276	14.92407